
The Influence of The Intensity of Using Tiktok Social Media on Student Learning Motivation

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ABSTRACT: The social media application TikTok is one of the social media that is much loved by the millennial generation, who incidentally is a student. This can influence two directions, namely positive and negative. In line with this, this study questions the direction of influence that exists on the Islamic University of Malang Islamic University of Ainul Yaqin Islamic Boarding School students. This research was conducted with a quantitative approach to the type of correlational research. Analysis of the data used was correlation analysis, which meant measuring the strength and closeness of the relationship. The sampling technique in this study used a simple random sampling technique. Data analysis techniques in hypotheses 1 and 2 used a simple correlation test. The main result of the quantitative research researchers need is how much social media TikTok can influence students' learning motivation at the Ainul Yaqin Campus Islamic Boarding School.

KEYWORDS: Correlation, intensity, learning motivation, Tiktok social media

INTRODUCTION

Along with the development of the times marked by technological advances, information, and communication in Indonesia, it should be equal to growth in the academic field (Chantika, 2018). However, what is happening now is the high use of social media dominated by students. Students tend to be more active in social relations through cyberspace because, since childhood, they have been introduced to technology and have good smartphone skills (Khrishananto & Adriansyah, 2021). In essence, technology was created to increase comfort and simplify human life. With the rapid advancement of technology today, almost no area of human life is free from its use, either directly or indirectly (Hidayatun, 2015). This development has resulted in an increase in fulfilling needs and the need for social media as one of the information supports in this modern era. In the development of social media, many applications are used, ranging from Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and many more. What is currently being discussed is the TikTok application. The TikTok application is quite interesting for the current generation, especially among teenagers who are students, because it fits perfectly with their lifestyle (Astuti & Andrini, 2021). TikTok is a social media platform in the form of audiovisual, and this platform allows users to listen, view and edit content according to the features available in the application (Harpina & Irfandi, 2023). This is a unique attraction because it can entertain users when they are tired and bored. The TikTok application offers many creative and innovative video-sharing experiences, thus attracting the attention of many users (Chasanah, 2021). In this application, many benefits are provided, including being able to interact in the comments column private chat, and even now, this application is also a business land because of the TikTok shop feature that students can utilize. In the world of education, the TikTok application, one of the social media loved by millennials who are students, can provide benefits. Quoted from Kompasiana, there are 3 benefits of the TikTok platform for students, namely first, as an information system from various domestic and foreign news; second, as an online-based learning media through content creators who use their TikTok accounts as a learning tool; and third, to increase friendship connections with other people from various educational backgrounds.

In line with the many benefits of this application, the question arises as to how it affects students' learning motivation. Excessive use can make students fall into unproductive usage patterns, spending valuable time so that they ignore their duties as students (Rahmawati, 2021). Time that should be used for learning is wasted. This can harm their motivation and learning outcomes. To achieve maximum learning achievement, it is necessary to focus on the lessons being carried out. According to Azizah (2022), to maximize learning, we need to focus and reduce distracting distractions such as gadget use. This is not in line with the adverse effects of unproductive TikTok application usage patterns. There are various previous studies on the influence of social media on learning motivation. However, research explicitly discussing the impact of the intensity of use of the TikTok application on student learning motivation is still limited. Therefore, this research is vital to get a more detailed discussion of how the influence of the

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intensity of using the TikTok application on learning outcomes for students, especially in a non-formal education environment such as the Ainul Yaqin Campus Pesantren, Islamic University of Malang.

However, researchers found one of the previous studies that examined the effect of the TikTok application on student learning motivation was conducted by Yuni Miftahul Chasanah, a university student of the State Islamic Institute (IAIN) Salatiga, in her final thesis. This research is very relevant to the research that researchers are currently doing. The results of the study concluded that the Tiktok application affected student learning motivation in the subject of demonstrating drama texts. In the learning process, this application positively influences student learning motivation at SMAN 1 Candroto. There is a correlation between learning interest and learning motivation. So, the better the use of TikTok social media, which has positive results on learning interest, the better student learning outcomes. In this study, data will be collected using questionnaires with students to obtain information about the intensity of TikTok use, things that motivate learning, and their learning patterns. To obtain data on learning outcomes that can support this research, documentation is taken with the teachers at the institution.

The results of this study are expected to provide an understanding. They can contribute to future research about the relationship between the use of the TikTok application and student learning motivation by providing direction and guidelines for managing time by using social media applications that are more effective for students. Based on the description above, the researchers raised the theme of "The Effect of Intensity of Use of TikTok Social Media on Student Motivation in Campus Pesantren Ainul Yaqin, Islamic University of Malang".

METHOD

This research was conducted using a quantitative approach with a correlational research type. In the preparation of instruments or data collection tools, the variables that became the main reference for researchers in compiling questionnaires consisted of questionnaires about the intensity of using TikTok and learning motivation at the research site. The data analysis used was correlation analysis. This research was conducted from June 14 to June 19, 2023, precisely at the Ainul Yaqin Campus Islamic Boarding School, Islamic University of Malang, Malang City, East Java. The research subjects in this study were Isti'dad students of Pesantren Ainul Yaqin Campus, Islamic University of Malang, in the academic year 2022/2023, totaling 114 students as a population and Isti'dad C and D classes totaling 64 people and 43 of them as samples. The 43 Mahasantri were all female. The sampling technique in this study used a simple random sampling technique. The data analysis technique in hypotheses 1 and 2 used a simple correlation test, where a simple correlation measured the relationship between two variables and determined the direction of the relationship. This correlation measured the relationship between the independent variable (X), namely the intensity of using TikTok, and the dependent variable (Y), namely learning motivation. To find out the correlation between the two variables, the help of SPSS V25 was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TikTok App

TikTok application is a social network and video music platform, this application was launched in September 2016 and developed by a Chinese developer named Zhang Yiming (Winarso, 2021). This application makes it easy for users to create, edit, and upload short videos and has various filters and supporting music.

Based on the 'Cloudflare Radar 2023 Year in Review' report, a list of the 10 most popular social media worldwide in 2023 was published. Interestingly, Facebook topped the list as the most popular social media in the world that year, while TikTok took second place (Sujatmiko, 2023). Although losing to Facebook, TikTok users have increased compared to last year. Business of Apps also noted that the TikTok application has been downloaded 748 million times throughout 2022, an increase of 0.94% compared to the previous year, where the application was downloaded 741 million times (Bayu, 2023).

This application, from the beginning of its launch until now, has stolen a lot of public attention, especially among school-age millennial teenagers who are commonly known as Generation Z. This application has a significant influence on its users, depending on how its users make the best use of this application.

Learning Motivation

Motivation comes from the word motive (motive), an active driving force. According to Purwanto (2006), a motive is a complex statement in an organism that directs an organism's behavior and actions that lead to a goal or stimulus. The process of playing a motive or activating a motive is called motivation. Learning motivation is essential because it is the driving aspect of each individual to do something to achieve a goal. According to McDonald (cited in Sartika, 2019), motivation is a change in energy in a person's personality characterized by the emergence of affective (feelings) and reactions to achieve goals. Thus, the emergence of motivation is characterized by a change in energy in a person that can be realized or not. According to Woodwort (cited in Sartika, 2019), a motive is a set that can make individuals carry out certain activities to achieve goals. Thus motivation is an impetus that can cause particular behaviors that are directed towards achieving certain goals. The behavior or action shown by a person in an effort to achieve specific goals depends on his motive.

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Meanwhile, Uno (2011) explains that motivation is related to (1) a hope of success in learning, (2) a spirit of achievement, and (3) a high desire to learn. Motivation is a series of efforts to provide certain conditions to create an impulse that makes someone want and want to do something. If he doesn't like it, he will try to negate or eliminate these feelings of dislike, so motivation here can be stimulated by external factors, but motivation grows within a person. Environment and living habits are one of the factors that can foster motivation in a person to learn.

THE EFFECT OF INTENSITY OF TIKTOK USE ON LEARNING OUTCOMES OF PKAY UNISMA STUDENTS

The results are obtained from the existing data by distributing questionnaires for the intensity of TikTok use and Santri learning motivation.

Table 1. Results of TikTok Usage Intensity Questionnaire Pondok Pesantren Ainul Yaqin, Universitas Islam Malang

Respondent Code	Value	Respondent Code	Value
R1	15	R23	12
R2	17	R24	17
R3	21	R25	15
R4	13	R26	17
R5	21	R27	17
R6	9	R28	21
R7	21	R29	12
R8	9	R30	18
R9	9	R31	13
R10	16	R32	17
R11	21	R33	14
R12	17	R34	25
R13	17	R35	14
R14	15	R36	14
R15	14	R37	21
R16	14	R38	16
R17	20	R39	14
R18	21	R40	16
R19	14	R41	17
R20	17	R42	17
R21	19	R43	14
R22	14		
Total			695
N			43
Average (M)			16
Standard Deviation (SD)			3,6

Table 1.1. Results of the Learning Motivation Questionnaire at Pondok Pesantren Ainul Yaqin, Universitas Islam Malang

Code Respondent	Value	Respondent Code	Value
R1	21	R23	20
R2	20	R24	23
R3	20	R25	20
R4	18	R26	24
R5	21	R27	23
R6	17	R28	22
R7	21	R29	23
R8	21	R30	20
R9	21	R31	18
R10	26	R32	21
R11	20	R33	19

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R12	24	R34	27
R13	22	R35	21
R14	21	R36	24
R15	19	R37	19
R16	21	R38	25
R17	28	R39	20
R18	26	R40	22
R19	19	R41	21
R20	25	R42	21
R21	24	R43	21
R22	18		
Total			927
N			43
Average (M)			22
Standard Deviation (SD)			2,5

From the data obtained, the next step is to perform calculations to determine the relationship between the intensity of TikTok use and learning motivation in Pondok Pesantren Ainul Yaqin, Universitas Islam Malang students.

a. Analysis of the validity of the research questionnaire

Based on the results of calculations using IBM SPSS V25 to test the validity of research on the intensity of using TikTok on learning motivation. From the results of $r_{count} > r_{table} = 0.301$ with $\alpha = 0.05$. The intensity of TikTok questions 2 through 5 on the questionnaire is valid, and the learning motivation questionnaire questions 1 through 6 are valid, so it is appropriate for research.

b. Reliability test

After doing the validity test, it will continue with the reliability test. So, based on the results of the reliability test that has been carried out, it will show Cronbach's alpha if the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$, is obtained:

- The questionnaire on the intensity of using TikTok at α 5% with n 43 obtained $r_{count} = 0.822$.
- The Learning Motivation Questionnaire at α 5% with n 43 obtained $r_{count} = 0.377$.

So, the instrument to be used for research is said to be reliable because $r_{count} > r_{table}$.

c. Prerequisite Test Analysis

After conducting a normality test using IBM SPSS V25, then the value of $\alpha = 0.05$, while the criteria for normality are as follows:

- If $x_{count} < 0.05$, then the data is normally distributed.
- If $x_{count} > 0.05$, then the data is normally distributed

Based on the significant value of $0.200 > 0.05$, it can be said that the data is usually said to be normally distributed data.

d. Hypothesis Test Results Based on the results that have been calculated with the help of IBM SPSS V25 with the condition that

- If the significance value of $t < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted,
- If the significance value of $t > 0.05$, then H_0 is accepted, and H_a is rejected.

Based on the results of the correlations table output, the sig value (2-tailed) = 0.050, then H_0 is REJECTED, meaning H_a is ACCEPTED, so it is concluded that there is a correlation between the intensity of using TikTok and the Motivation to Study at Pesantren Kampus Ainul Yaqin. While the value of person correlations is 0.308, meaning that it shows a positive relationship, while the correlation coefficient of 0.308 can be concluded that the correlation value is LOW because it is in the range of 0.200 - 0.399.

CONCLUSION

With reference to the results of research and studies conducted, there is a significant influence between Tiktok Intensity and Learning Motivation at Ainul Yaqin Islamic Boarding School with a Sig value of 0.005, then accepting H_a and rejecting H_0 . This study has a degree of relationship in the weak correlation category in the Pearson Correlation value between 0.21 to 0.40, namely 0.308. It is concluded that there is an influence between the intensity of using TikTok. The influence is positive, with a weak categorization.

REFERENCES

- 1) Astuti, E., & Andriani, S. (2021). Intensity of Use of the Tiktok Application on Adolescent Imitation Behavior. *Communicology: Scientific Journal of Communication Sciences*, 18(2), 134-142.
- 2) Azizah, Z. N. (2022). To Stay Focused, Here are 5 Ways to Maintain Concentration. *Yoursay.Id*. <https://yoursay.suara.com/lifestyle/2022/04/18/151519/biarstay-focused-here-are-5-ways-to-keep-concentration>

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- 3) Bayu, D. (2023). Active TikTok users in the world will reach 1.6 billion by 2022. DataIndonesia.Id. <https://dataindonesia.id/internet/detail/pengguna-aktiftiktok-world-touch-16-billion-by-2022>.
- 4) Chantika, P. D. (2018). The Relationship between Intensity of Use of Line Social Media and Learning Motivation with Student Learning Achievement.
- 5) Chasanah, Y. M. (2021). The Effect of Intensity of Use of Tiktok Application on Learning Motivation of Class XI SMAN 1 Candiroto. State Islamic Institute (IAIN) Salatiga.
- 6) Harpina, & Irfandi, M. A. (2023). The Effect of Tiktok Social Media on the Learning Achievement of Class V A Students of Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri (MIN) 1 Bulukumba. *FIKRUNA: Scientific Journal of Education and Society*, 5(1), 1-19.
- 7) Hidayatun, U. (2015). The Effect of Intensity of Social Media Use and Peer Support on Consumptive Behavior in Class XI Students of SMA Muhammadiyah 3 Yogyakarta. *E-Journal of Guidance and Counseling*, 10(4), 1- 13.
- 8) Khrihananto, R., & Adriansyah, M. A. (2021). The Effect of Intensity of Instagram Social Media Use and Conformity on Consumptive Behavior among Generation Z. *Journal of Imiah Psychology*, 9(2), 323-336. <https://doi.org/10.30872/psikoborneo>
- 9) Purwanto, M. N. (2006). *Psychology of Education. Teenage Workshop*.
- 10) Rahmawati, I. (2021). The Effect of Tik Tok Social Media on the Learning Achievement of Grade IV Students of SDN 1 Panjangrejo, Bantul Regency. *STKIP Bima Education Journal*, 3(2), 33-40. <https://doi.org/10.33627/gg.v3i2.497>
- 11) Sartika, R. (2019). The Effect of Learning Strategies and Learning Motivation on Akidah Akhlak Learning Outcomes of MIN Sei Mati Medan Students (Vol. 2, Issue 1) [UIN North Sumatra Medan]. <http://www.scopus.com/inward/record.url?eid=2s2.0.84865607390&partnerID=tZOtx3y1%0Ahttp://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=2LIMMD9FVXkC&oi=fnd&pg=PR5&dq=Principles+of+Digital+Image+Processing+fundamental+techniques&ots=H jrHeuS>
- 12) Sujatmiko, T. (2023). Beat TikTok, Google Most Popular Internet Service 2022. Cloudflare version. Krjogja.Com. <https://www.krjogja.com/angkringan/read/487483/kalahkan-tiktok-googlepopular-internet-services-2022-cloudflare-version>
- 13) Uno, H. B. (2011). *Motivation Theory and Its Measurement*. Bumi Aksara. Winarso, B. (2021). What is TikTok and What are its Features? DailySocial.Id. <https://dailysocial.id/post/apa-itu-tik-to>